

CROATIAN FEMININE PROPER NAMES WITH LATIN ORIGIN AND THEIR EQUIVALENTS OF CROATIAN ORIGIN

[Gergana PETKOVA](#)

Senior Lecturer, Ph. D.

(Medical University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria)

gi4e82ap@abv.bg

[Vanya IVANOVA](#)

Associate Professor, Ph. D.

(“Paisii Hilendarski” University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria)

Abstract

The research object of the present text is feminine Croatian proper names, derived from an appellative, Latin by origin, and Croatian anthroponyms that represent translated equivalents of the previous ones. The main aim is their full list to be presented and their initial meaning as well, both the Latin and the Croatian.

Keywords: *Croatian feminine proper name, Latin feminine proper name, origin, equivalent, onomastics*

Rezumat

În articol, propunem o cercetare a numelor proprii de persoane de sex feminin, care se întâlnesc în limba croată și care provin atât de la nume similare din limba latină, cât și sunt o traducere a acestora în limba croată.

Cuvinte-cheie: *nume proprii de persoane de sex feminin, care se întâlnesc în limba croată; nume proprii feminine în limba latină, origine, echivalent, onomastică*

The research object of the present text is feminine 36 Croatian proper names (including all their variants found in the anthroponymic dictionaries), derived from an appellative, Latin by origin, and 31 Croatian proper names that represent equivalents of the previous ones, Croatian by origin. The main aim is to present a full list of both Latin and Croatian onyms as well as their initial meaning.

Rječnik osobnih imena by Mate Šimundić (1988) and *Rječnik suvremenih hrvatskih osobnih imena* by Ankica Čilaš Šimpraga, Dubravka Ivšić Majić and Domagoj Vidocić (2018) are used as a main source of information for excerpting the researched anthroponyms. All the necessary information about the researched onyms can be found there – etymology, forms, derivational process, etc.

The researched proper names are divided into three major groups according to:

- 1) the meaning of the appellative (i. e. a thematic classification or if the appellative is used to name a feature of the character (good or bad), a feature of the body, etc.);

- 2) the function of the name to protect the new-born or to wish him/ her good fortune, used in the old folk tradition;
- 3) their canonization.

All of the personal names derived from a Latin appellative that are included in this paper are part of the modern anthroponymicon. However, their initial meaning is not perfectly clear to the common people nowadays and it is not very easy to recognize and find out the link between the proper names presented in the two groups divided according to the origin of the basic appellative, i. e. if it is Latin or Croatian. That is why it would be very interesting and helpful to show it.

The extralinguistic information about the canonization is also of great importance. This is one of the possible reasons why some Roman mythological, gentile names, cognomens, and Neolatin anthroponyms continue to be alive and well-spread among modern Croatians. Nevertheless, their function now as saints' names is somehow different and their initial meaning and usage is faded or forgotten.

Today, a very popular trend can be observed for parents to choose the so-called *international names* for their newborn children so that the child would not have problems in the future if he/ she wants to change the country of living. That fashion is valid not only for Croatians but for all Europeans too. And, obviously, most of the mentioned above names are Latin by origin. But do parents know what the initial meaning of a given personal name is? Is there a Croatian equivalent of the same anthroponym that is probably forgotten but, surely, more familiar? This paper may be of assistance to find the answers to these problems.

Classification of the Feminine Croatian Proper Names in Thematic Groups

We distinguish the following groups of Croatian proper names:

- (a) *anthroponyms, giving information about a feature of the human appearance:*
- *Bela* (< *bela* - "white")/*Alba, Albe, Albana, Albina* (< *albinus, 3* - "white"; *albus, 3* - "white");
 - *Bogana* (< *bog* - "god")/*Dea* (< *dea, ae, f* - "goddess");
 - *Cveta* (< *cvet* - "flower")/*Florisia, Florita, Flosina* (< *flos, oris, m* - "flower");
 - *Gospana* (< *gospa, gospođa, gospodarica* - "mistress")/*Domina, Domna* (< *domna, ae, f/ domina, ae, f* - "mistress");
 - *Jasna* (< *jasna* - "clear")/*Klara* (*clara* - "clear" (feminine form of the adjective *clarus, 3* - "clear");
 - *Lepa* (< *lepa* - "beautiful")/*Lijepa* (< *lijepa* - "beautiful")/*Bela* (< *bella* - "beautiful" (feminine form of the adjective *bellus, 3* - "beautiful");
 - *Ljerka* (< *lijer* (*lilium candidum*) - "lily")/*Lilija, Lilijana* (< *lilium, ii, n* - "lily");
 - *Maslina* (< *maslina* - "olive")/*Oliva* (< *oliva, ae, f* - "olive");

- *Medvedica* (< *medvedica* - "she-bear"), *Medvojedica* (< *medvojedica* - "she-bear")/*Ursa* (< *ursa*, ae, f - "she-bear");
- *Nebesna* (< *nebesna* - "heavenly")/*Celesta*, *Celestina* (< *caelestis* - "heavenly");
- *Ruža*, *Ruže* (< *ruža* - "rose")/*Rosa*, *Rosalija* (< *rosa*, ae, f - "rose");
- *Ubava* (< *ubava* - "beautiful")/*Bela* (< *bella* - "beautiful" (feminine form of the adjective *bellus*, 3 - "beautiful");
- *Zvezda* (< *zvezda* - "star")/*Stela* (< *stella*, ae, f - "star");
- *Živa* (< *živa* - "alive")/*Viva* (< *viva* - "alive" (feminine form of the adjective *vivus*, 3 - "alive").

These features may be, for example, about:

- the skin colour: *Bela*/*Alba*, *Albe*, *Albana*, *Albina* (with light complexion);
- the physical beauty: *Bogana*/*Dea* (as handsome as a god); *Čveta*/*Florisa*, *Florita*, *Flosina* (as handsome as a flower);
- the physical strength (*Medvedica*, *Medvojedica*/*Ursa* (to become as strong as a bear);
- the vividness: *Živa*/*Viva* (to be healthy and to live long), etc.

It should be mentioned that the features of the human appearance may or may not be positive.

(b) *anthroponyms*, giving information about a feature of the human character:

- *Dobrana* (< *dobra* - "good")/*Bona* (< *bonus*, 3 - "good"), i. e. to become a good person;
- *Dušana* (< *duša* - "soul")/*Anima* (< *anima*, ae, f - "soul"), i. e. to be a person with a good character;
- *Pesma* (< *pesma* - "song"), *Pjesma* (< *pjesma* - "song")/*Karmen* (< *carmen*, inis, n - "song"), i. e. to be joyful like a song;
- *Pobeda* (< *pobeda* - "victory"), *Pobjeda* (< *pobjeda* - "victory")/*Viktorija* (< *victoria*, ae, f - "victory"), i. e. to become with a victorious character;
- *Radosna* (< *radosna* - "happy")/*Felicitas* (< *felix*, icis - "happy"), i. e. to be happy;
- *Radostija* (< *radost* - "joy")/*Felicitas* (< *felicitas*, tatis, f - "joy"), i. e. to be happy;
- *Slavena* (< *slava* - "glory")/*Glorija* (< *gloria*, ae, f - "glory"), i. e. to become a glorious person;
- *Slavna* (< *slavna* - "glorious")/*Gloriosa* (< *gloriosa* - "glorious" (feminine form of the adjective *gloriosus*, 3 - "glorious"), i. e. to become a glorious person;

(c) *anthroponyms*, giving information about the birth of the person:

- *Osmenka* (< *osma* - "eighth")/*Oktavija* (< *octava* - "eighth" (feminine form of the adjective *octavus*, 3 - "eighth"), i. e. the eighth child born in a given family;
- *Proena* (< *proa* - "first")/*Prima* (< *prima* - "first" (feminine form of the adjective *primus*, 3 - "first"), i. e. the first child born in a given family;

- *Rođena* (< *rođena, roditi* – “born”)/*Natalija* (< *natalis, e* – “born”), born alive;
- *Svetana* (< *sveta* – “holly”)/*Santa* (< *sancta, ae, f/ sancta* – “holly” (feminine form of the adjective *sanctus, 3* – “holly”), i.e. born on a holy day;
- *Zorana* (< *zora* – “dawn”)/*Aurora* (< *aurora, ae, f* – “dawn”), i. e. born at dawn.

Classification of the Feminine Croatian Proper Names According to their Function to Protect the New-Born or to Wish Him/Her Good Fortune, Used in the Old Folklore Tradition

We can find here:

- *protective names: Medvoedica, Medvojedica/Ursa, Osmenka/Oktavija* (naming the child like that may be accepted as parents' wish the eighth child to be the last one born in a given family);
- *names, used to wish the new-born good fortune: Bela/Alba, Albe, Albana, Albina; Bogana/Dea; Cveta/Floris, Florita, Flosina; Dobrana/Bona; Dušana/Anima; Gospana/Domina, Domna; Jasna/Klara; Lepa/Lijepa/Bela; Ljerka/Lilija, Lilijana; Maslina/Oliva; Nebesna/Celesta, Celestina; Pesma, Pjesma/Karmen; Pobeda, Pobjeda/Viktorija; Provena/Prima; Radosna/Felicitas; Radostija/Felicitas; Rođena/Natalija; Ruža, Ruže/Rosa, Rosalija; Slavena/Glorija; Slavna/Gloriosa; Svetana/Santa; Ubava/Bela; Zorana/Aurora; Zvezda/Stela; Živa/Viva.*

The researched anthroponyms may be divided into two major groups according to their semantics – names that somehow protect the baby from death, diseases, something evil, etc., and names that wish him/ her to be handsome/ beautiful, kind, strong, healthy, victorious, happy, brave, to live long, and so on. A word denoting flowers, herbs, trees, fruits, birds, and animals is usually used as a basic appellative for those names. It is often very difficult to impose limitations between these two groups due to the fact that an anthroponym may be regarded as part of the first group as well as of the second one.

Classification of the Feminine Croatian Proper Names According to their Canonization

These names are:

- *names of saints, canonized by the Catholic church: Albina, Klara, Santo;*
- *names of saints, canonized by the Catholic as well as the Orthodox church: Bona, Natalija, Ursa, Viktorija.*

Conclusions

There are 3 subgroups according to the thematic classification:

- anthroponyms, giving information about a feature of the human appearance (40 anthroponyms, 17 Croatian by origin and 23 Latin by origin);

- anthroponyms, giving information about a feature of the human character (17 anthroponyms, 9 Croatian by origin and 8 Latin by origin);
- anthroponyms, giving information about the birth of the person (10 anthroponyms, 5 Croatian by origin and 5 Latin by origin).

There are 2 subgroups according to the function of the name to protect the new-born (5 anthroponyms, 3 Croatian by origin and 2 Latin by origin), and according to the function or to wish him/her good fortune (62 anthroponyms, 28 Croatian by origin and 34 Latin by origin).

There are 2 subgroups according to the canonization of the researched proper names:

- male names of saints, canonized by the Catholic church (3 anthroponyms);
- male names of saints, canonized by the Catholic church as well as by the Orthodox one (4 anthroponyms).

All of the anthroponyms included in both classification groups are Latin by origin.

NOTA BENE: The majority of the researched anthroponyms may be found in the latest Croatian dictionary of proper names, *Rječnik suvremenih hrvatskih osobnih imena* by Ankica Čilaš Šimpraga, Dubravka Ivšić Majić and Domagoj Vidocić, published in 2018. It prompts us that though being with a rare usage, the proper names that represent a scientific interest in the present text, are still vivid and part of the contemporary Croatian anthroponymicon.

Index of the Croatian Feminine Proper Names with Latin Origin and their Croatian by Origin Equivalents

BELA (Belana, Belava, Belča, Belka, Belojka, Beluna, Belunka, Bijela, Bijelka, Bjela, Bjelana, Bjelava, Bjelica, Bjelka) (< *belā* - "white")/ ALBA (1, 3, 4)/ ALBE (4) (Albiana (1), Albica (4), Albijana (1, 4), Albijanda (1), Albijanica, Albijanka, Albita, Albitica (4)); ALBANA (2, 4) (Albanica (4)); ALBINA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Albinica, Albinka (4), Albona, Alibiana (1)) (< *alba* - "white" (feminine form of the adjective *albus*, 3 - "white") (1, 4));

BOGANA (Bogica, Boginja, Bogojka, Boguša, Božana, Božanka) (< *bog* - "god")/ DEA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Deana, Deanka (1), Deata, Deatica, Deica (4), Dea (1, 4), Dejica, Dejina, Dejka, Deka, Dekica, Deša, Dešica, Deška (4)) (< *dea, ae, f* - "goddess" (1, 4));

CVETA (Cvetana, Cvetanka, Cvetija, Cvetina, Cvetinka, Cvetka, Cvijeta, Cvijetka, Cvita, Cvitana, Cvitanka, Cvitka, Cvjeta, Cvjetana, Cvjetanka, Cvjetka, Četana) (< *coet* - "flower")/ FLORISA (Floriska); FLORITA (Floritica); FLOSINA (Flosinica, Flosinka) (< *flos, oris, m* - "flower" (3, 4));

DOBRANA (Dobrena, Dobrenka, Dobreta, Dobrija, Dobrila, Dobrina, Dobrinka, Dobrinja, Dobrinjka, Dobruna, Dobrunka, Dobruša, Dobruška) (< *dobra* - "good")/ BONA (1, 2, 4) (Bone (1), Boneta (1, 4), Bonetica, Bonetta, Bonica, Bonina, Bonislava, Bonita, Bonitica, Bonitta (4), Bonka (1, 4), Bonkica (1)) (< *bona* - "good" (feminine form of the adjective *bonus*, 3 - "good") (1, 4));

DUŠANA (Dušanija, Dušanka, Dušenka) (< *duša* - "soul")/ ANIMA (Animica, Animka) (< *anima, ae, f* - "soul" (4));

GOSPANA (Gospava, Gospina, Gospodinka, Gospođinka, Gospojinka) (< *gospa, gospođa, gospodarica* - "mistress")/ DOMINA (1, 3, 4)/ DOMNA (Dominikija, Dominka, Domnica, Domnika, Domnikica) (< *domna, ae, f / domina, ae, f* - "mistress" (4));

JASNA (Jasnica) (< *jasna* - "clear")/ KLARA (1, 3, 4) (Clara, Clarissa, Klarena, Klarica, Klarika (4), Klarisa (1, 2, 4)) (< *clara* - "clear" (feminine form of the adjective *clarus*, 3 - "clear") (1, 4));

LEPA (Lepana, Lepava, Lepica, Lepka) (< *lepa* - "beautiful"); LIJEPA (Lijepijana) (< *lijepa* - "beautiful")/ BELA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Belaja, Belana, Belava, Belavka, Belča (1), Belica (1, 4), Belika, Belina, Belinda, Belisava, Belislava (1), Belita, Belitica, Belitka (4), Belka (1, 4), Belkica, Bella (4), Belna, Belojka, Belona, Belosava, Beloslava, Beluna, Belunka, Beluša, Belja, Beljana, Bjela, Bjelaja (1)) (< *bella* - "beautiful" (feminine form of the adjective *bellus*, 3 - "beautiful") (1, 4));

LJERKA (Ljerkica, Ljercica) (< *lijer* (*lilium candidum*) - "lily")/ LILIJA (1, 3, 4) (Lilijica (4), Lilika, Lilita, Lilka, Lilja, Ljlja (1), Ljljina (4), Ljulja (1)); LILIJANA (1, 3, 4) (Liliana (2, 4), Lilijanica, Lilijanka (4), Liljana (1, 4), Liljanica, Liljanka (4), Ljerka (2), Ljljana (1, 2, 4), Ljljanče, Ljiljanica (4), Ljljanka (1, 4), Ljuljana (1)) (< *lilium, ii, n* - "lily" (4));

MASLINA (Maslinica, Maslinka) (< *maslina* - "olive")/ OLIVA (Olivia (1, 4), Olivica (4), Olivija (1, 4), Olivijica (4)) (< *oliva, ae, f* - "olive" (1, 4));

MEDVEDICA (< *medvedica* - "she-bear"); MEDVJEDICA (< *medvjedica* - "she-bear")/ URSA (1, 4) (Ursica, Ursina, Ursinica, Ursinija, Ursinka (4), Urša (1, 4), Uršica, Urška, Urza, Urzica (4)) (< *ursa, ae, f* - "she-bear" (1, 4));

NEBESNA (< *nebesna* - "heavenly")/ CELESTA (4); CELESTINA (Čelestina (1, 4), Kelestina (1)) (< *caelestis* - "heavenly" (4));

OSMENKA (Osmenkica) (< *osma* - "eighth")/ OKTAVIJA (1, 2, 4) (Oktavijica, Oktavina, Oktavinica, Otavija, Otavijica, Ottavia (4)) (< *octava* - "eighth" (feminine form of the adjective *octavus*, 3 - "eighth") (1, 4));

PESMA (Pesmica) (< *pesma* - "song"); PJESMA (Pjesmica) (< *pjesma* - "song")/ KARMEN (< *carmen, inis, n* - "song" (1));

POBEDA (Pobedica) (< *pobeda* - "victory"); POBJEDA (Pobjedica) (< *pobjeda* - "victory")/ VIKTORIJA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Victoria (2), Viktorijica, Viktorica, Viktorika, Vitorija, Vitorijica, Vittoria (4)) (< *victoria, ae, f* - "victory" (1, 4));

PRVENA (Prvenka) (< *prova* - "first")/ PRIMA (< *prima* - "first" (feminine form of the adjective *primus*, 3 - "first") (1));

RADOSNA (Radosnica) (< *radosna* - "happy")/ FELICITAS (4) (Feliceta, Felicita (1, 2, 4), Felicitata, Félicité, Felisita) (< *felix, icis* - "happy" (4));

RADOSTIJA (Radostina) (< *radost* - "joy")/ FELICITAS (4) (Feliceta (2), Felicita (1, 2, 4), Felicitata, Félicité, Felisita) (< *felicitas, tatis, f* - "joy" (4));

ROĐENA (Rođenka) (< *rođena, roditi* – “born”)/ NATALIJA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Nadalina (2, 4), Nadalinica, Nadalinka, Natajla, Natajlica (4), Natalia (1), Natali (2, 4), Natalia, Natalie, Natalijica (4), Natalina (2, 4), Natalinica, Natalinka, Noela, Noelica (4), Noelle (2), Noëlle) (< *natalis, e* – “born” (4));

RUŽA/ RUŽE (Ružana, Ružica, Ružova, Ruška, Ruškica) (< *ruža* – “rose”)/ ROSA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Rosalina, Rosalinka, Rosana, Rosanica (4), Rosanka, Rose (1, 4), Roseta, Rosetica, Rosetta, Rosica (4), Rosija, Rosika, Rosina (1, 4), Rosinica, Rosinka, Rosita, Rositica, Rositta (4), Roska, Roza (1, 4), Rozali (1), Rozalina (4), Rozalinda (1), Rozalinka (4), Rozana (1, 4), Rozanica (4), Rozanka (1, 4), Roze (1), Rozena (4), Roze-ta (1, 4), Rozetica (4), Rozi (1), Rozica, Rozika, Rozina (1, 4), Rozinda (1), Rozinica, Rozinka (4), Rozita (1, 4), Rozitica (4), Rozmena, Rozmenka (1), Rozmira, Rozmirka, Rozomira, Rozomirka (4), Roža (1, 4), Rožena, Roženka (1), Rožica, Rožika (4), Rožina (1, 4), Rožinica, Rožinka (4)); ROSALIJA (1, 4)/ ROSARIJA (4) (Rosalia (1, 4), Rosalijica (4), Rozalija (1, 2, 4), Rozalijica (4), Rožalija (1, 4), Rožalijica, Rosaria, Rosarijica, Rozarija, Rozarijica, Rožarija, Rožarijica (4), Rusalija (1), Ruzarija (2, 4), Ruzarijica, Ružarija, Ružarijica (4)) (< *rosa, ae, f* – “rose” (2, 4);

SLAVENA (Slavica, Slavka, Slavenka, Slavija, Slavijana, Slavijanka, Slavijica, Slavina, Slavinka, Slavkica, Slavojka) (< *slava* – “glory”)/ GLORIJA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Gloria (1, 4), Glorijeta (1), Glorijica (4)) (< *gloria, ae, f* – “glory” (1, 4));

SLAVNA (Slavnica) (< *slavna* – “glorious”)/ GLORIOSA (Gloriosica (4), Glorioza (1)) (< *gloriosa* – “glorious” (feminine form of the adjective *gloriosus*, 3 – “glorious”) (1, 4));

SVETANA (Svetanka, Svetanija, Svetina, Svetinka) (< *sveta* – “holly”)/ SANTA (1, 4) (Santeja (1), Santica (4), Santina (1, 4), Santinica, Santuca, Santuzza, Šanta, Šantica (4), Senta (1)) (< *sancta, ae, f/ sancta* – “holly” (feminine form of the adjective *sanctus*, 3 – “holly”) (1, 4));

UBAVA (Ubavica, Ubavenka, Ubavka, Ubavkica) (< *ubava* – “beautiful”)/ BELA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Belaja, Belana, Belava, Belavka, Belča (1), Belica (1, 4), Belika, Belina, Belinda, Belisava, Belislava (1), Belita, Belitica, Belitka (4), Belka (1, 4), Belkica, Bella (4), Belna, Belojka, Belona, Belosava, Beloslava, Beluna, Belunka, Beluša, Belja, Beljana, Bjela, Bjelaja (1)) (< *bella* – “beautiful” (feminine form of the adjective *bellus*, 3 – “beautiful”) (1, 4));

ZORANA (Zoranče, Zoranica, Zoranka, Zoreta, Zoretica, Zorica, Zorijana, Zorijanica, Zorijanka, Zorika, Zorina, Zorinka, Zorjana, Zorjanica, Zorjanka, Zorka, Zorkača, Zorkelja, Zorkena, Zorketa, Zorketina, Zorkica, Zorkota) (< *zora* – “dawn”)/ AURO-RA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Aurorica, Avrora, Avrорica, Avrorka (4)) (< *aurora, ae, f* – “dawn” (1, 4));

ZVEZDA (Zvezdana, Zvezdanica, Zvezdanka, Zvezdica, Zvijezda, Zvijezdica, Zvezdana, Zvezdanica, Zvezdanka, Zvezdica) (< *zvezda* – “star”)/ STELA (1, 2, 3, 4) (Estela (2, 4), Estelica, Estelka, Estella (4), Stelica (1, 4), Stella, Stelluzza, Steluca (4)) (< *stella, ae, f* – “star” (1, 4));

ŽIVA (1, 3) (Živadina, Živadinka, Živana, Živanija, Živanka, Živica, Živka, Živna, Živojka) (< *živa* – “alive”)/ VIVA (Vivana, Viviana, Vivija, Vivijana, Vivka) (< *viva* – “alive” (feminine form of the adjective *vivus*, 3 – “alive”) (1)).

References

- Bosanac, M. (1984). *Prosvjetin imenoslov*. Prosvjeta.
- Marević, J. (1994). *Hrvatsko-latinski rječnik*. Školska knjiga.
- Šimpraga, A., Č., Majić, D., I., Vidocić, D. (2018). *Rječnik suvremenih hrvatskih osobnih imena*. Institut za hrvatski jezik i jezikoslovije.
- Šimundić, M. (1988). *Rječnik osobnih imena*. Nakladni zavod Matice hrvatske.